

Awareness Conceptualisation for New-Generation Collaborative Environments (NGCE)

Awareness Conceptualisation		Concepts and Interpretation
Area	Dimension	
Team	Presence	People & groups availability; Tele-presence
	Identity	People & groups identification; Avatars; Authoring of artefacts
	Social structure	Group structure; Social organizations; Roles; Privileges
	AI Agents & robots	Software bots; Intelligent robots; Multi-agents
Activity	Tasks & Actions	Goals & subgoals; Workspaces; Task allocation
	Information & Knowledge	Artifacts; Documents; Object models & representations
	Tools	Working tools; Computational resources; Workspaces
	Situation	Global perception; Environment; Scenario; Action sphere
	Workflows	Transitions; Management of coupling
Communication	Conversations	Chats; Instant messaging, Audio channels; Speech synthesis
	Gestures & Body language	Gesture recognition; Casual interaction
	Other communication methods	Videoconferencing; Automated language interpreters; Communication through avatars
Coordination	Coordination of Actions	Interaction protocols and patterns; Access control; Constraints; Fine-grained prerequisites
	Task Sequencing	Interdependences & conflicts; Prerequisites
	Planning	High level coordination
Interaction	Time	Time in which things happen; Asynchronous vs Synchronous; Historical activity
	Style	Interaction style; Explicit vs Implicit; Interaction metaphors
	Feedback & Feedthrough	Interaction effects; Cues and visual signals; Sound alerts
Place & Space	Location	Place; Workplace; Geolocation
	Mobility	Transitions between spaces; Mobility between locations
	Scenario	Virtual scenarios; Real-world scenarios; Digital scenarios; Spatial metaphors; 2D/3D spaces
	Environmental conditions	Climatic conditions; Natural spaces; Scents and sounds in nature
Affective state	Mood	A long-lasting emotional state that influences perception and behaviour
	Feelings	Subjective emotional experiences that arise in response to thoughts, memories, or interactions
	Sensations	Physical perceptions from sensory inputs

References

Bravo, C., Molina, A.I., Gallardo, J., Ortega-Cordovilla, M. (2025) [Conceptualisation of Collaboration Awareness in Next-Generation Collaborative Environments](#). IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC), Vienna, Austria, 2025, pp. 5813-5820